

Thermogravimetric Analysis of Some 1 : 4 Adducts of Organotin Halides

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Received 8 September 1970; Revised MSS received 1 September 1971; accepted for publication 7 February 1972

Organotin halides are known to yield 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 adducts with bases in general¹. Some other adducts such as $R_2SnX_2 \cdot 4L$ and $R_4SnX_4 \cdot 4L$ (1 : 4) have also been described²⁻⁶. Earlier reports have mentioned that these adducts contain only two coordinating ligand molecules. Davies⁷, however, has reported an adduct where tin is believed to be in octa-coordination state. To elucidate their structure further the probable mode of decomposition of $nPrSnCl_3 \cdot 4\gamma$ -Picoline, $Ph_2SnCl_2 \cdot 4\gamma$ -Picoline, $PhSnCl_3 \cdot 4\gamma$ -Picoline, $nPrSnCl_3 \cdot 4$ Morpholine, $Ph_2SnCl_2 \cdot 4$ -Morpholine and $PhSnCl_3 \cdot 4$ Morpholine has been studied by thermogravimetric analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

These adducts were prepared by the methods described earlier⁴⁻⁶. The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a 'STANTON thermo recording balance', model AD-2, operating at a heating rate of 4°/minute. The thermogravimetric curves were scanned on chart No. H₄, run at a speed of six inches per hour and the results summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

S.No.	Names of the Adducts	Initial decomposition temperature (°C)	% weight loss to get 1 : 2 adduct		% weight of the residue	
			Found	Required	Found	Required for SnO ₂
1.	$nPrSnCl_3 \cdot 4\gamma$ -Picoline	200	29.60	29.07	23.46	23.58
2.	$nPrSnCl_3 \cdot 4$ -Morpholine	100	—	28.06	24.32	24.49
3.	$Ph_2SnCl_2 \cdot 4\gamma$ -Picoline	50	26.53	26.21	20.94	21.09
4.	$Ph_2SnCl_2 \cdot 4$ -Morpholine	50	—	25.14	21.81	21.82
5.	$PhSnCl_3 \cdot 4\gamma$ -Picoline	100	28.20	27.57	22.47	22.39
6.	$PhSnCl_3 \cdot 4$ Morpholine	90	—	26.34	23.19	23.21

Percentage weight loss per five minutes interval has been plotted as a function of temperature and the resulting 'thermal decomposition curves' presented in Figs. 1 and 2.

Chlorine was not detected in the final residue in any of the experiments. The residue, SnO_2 , left over in every experiment was found to correspond to the tin content of the original complex taken.

DISCUSSION

The results indicate that the complexes do not undergo any weight loss below 30° . On further heating, however, the decomposition begins at specific temperatures depending upon their thermal stabilities. Those with sharp and definite melting points undergo small weight loss before melting whereas others which melt with decomposition record appreciable weight loss before reaching their melting points during thermogravimetric analysis.

Higher the temperature required for the initial decomposition of the complex, greater will be its thermal stability. Taking this as a criterion for the thermal stability of these adducts, the order of their stabilities may be shown as :

The adducts under investigation have Sn←N, Sn-C and Sn-Cl linkages. The Sn←N bonds being somewhat weaker than the other two linkages, the base molecules are likely to be eliminated at comparatively lower temperatures. Furthermore, in these 1 : 4 adducts if all the base molecules are not bonded similarly, with the rise in temperature, the weaker bonds must be eliminated earlier than others, leading to the formation of some intermediate product which may be indicated by the break in the thermogravimetric curves.

The first figure represents the thermal decomposition curves of $n\text{PrSnCl}_3.4\gamma\text{-Picoline}$, $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2.4\gamma\text{-Picoline}$ and $\text{PhSnCl}_3.4\gamma\text{-Picoline}$. Appearance of breaks in these curves indicates the formation of intermediate di-adducts. But none of these di-adducts seems to be stable at these respective temperatures as the decomposition continues further with the rise in temperature. The elimination of the two $\gamma\text{-picoline}$ molecules at comparatively lower temperatures suggests that these two base molecules are less strongly held and may thus be linked differently.

In the second figure, the 'thermal decomposition curves' of $n\text{PrSnCl}_3.4\text{Morpholine}$, $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2.4\text{Morpholine}$ and $\text{PhSnCl}_3.4\text{Morpholine}$ have been represented. The breaks in the thermal decomposition curves do not coincide with any specific composition and, therefore, the probable composition of the intermediates remains unknown. It may probably be due to the reasons that in such cases both the acidic and the basic components undergo simultaneous decomposition. In these adducts also, there is no evidence for the thermal stability of any intermediate, as no zero weight loss horizontal level has been detected during their decomposition.

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